

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 3.3

LandSense Engagement Platform I

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LandSense Engagement Platform
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Short Description:
This report provides a summary of the current state of the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP). Descriptions of the Authorization Server, Federation, and core services are highlighted in this supplemental report. The public demonstrator version of the LEP is accessible via https://lep.landseuse.eu
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Executive Summary

The LandSense Engagement Platform brings together solutions that contribute to the transfer, assessment, valuation, uptake and exploitation of Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) data and related results of the LandSense project. The platform offers collaborative data collection and mapping functionalities allowing citizens and stakeholders to collect, view, analyse and share data from different. In addition, the LandSense Engagement Platform exposes various services that are useful to developers and innovators dealing with citizen science and LULC. The platform is accessible to anyone, but some features are only available to logged-in users. To facilitate the uptake of the platform, login is possible using several social media accounts, LandSense partner accounts and academic institutions participating in eduGAIN.

The LandSense Engagement Platform is accessible via <https://lep.landense.eu>

1 Introduction to LandSense

The Earth Observation (EO) data economy is moving towards becoming a highly competitive market segment. Solution providers are reliant on high-quality data as they need to deliver contextually appropriate EO-based value-added products and services. Currently within the EU's EO monitoring framework, there is a need for low-cost methods for acquiring high quality in-situ data to create accurate and well-validated environmental monitoring products. Timely acquisition and processing of high-quality *in-situ* data plays a critical role in ensuring that EO data and resultant EO-based products are properly calibrated and validated. To help address this need, LandSense is building a citizen observatory to link remote sensing data with modern participatory data collection methods that involve citizen scientists for improved environmental monitoring. The LandSense Citizen Observatory is fostered through innovative and novel EO mobile applications, allowing citizens to not only play a key role in LULC monitoring, but also to be directly involved in the co-creation of such solutions.

A series of LandSense tools and services accessible via the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP) will be demonstrated across a series of campaigns to illustrate the power and flexibility of the LandSense CO to tackle different environmental monitoring issues.

- The **Urban Landscape Dynamics** theme focuses on engaging citizens via mobile applications to discover land change in urban and peri-urban areas. Pilot cases will be implemented in Amsterdam, Toulouse, Vienna and Heidelberg to engage citizens in monitoring their local environment.
- The **Agriculture Land Use** theme focuses on leveraging the power of EO systems and advanced crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value added services to European farmers and public authorities in the agricultural sector. Demonstration cases are planned for Serbia.
- The **Forest & Habitat Monitoring** theme will trigger volunteer networks for in-situ data collection to help monitor protected areas within BirdLife International Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs) and Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) through networks in Spain and Indonesia.

The following document provides an overview of the key components and functionality of the LandSense Engagement Platform.

2 The LandSense Engagement Platform

An important part of the LandSense Citizen Observatory is the LandSense Engagement Platform (Figure 1), a service platform comprised of highly marketable EO-based solutions that contribute to the transfer, assessment, valuation, uptake and exploitation of LULC data and related results. The platform offers collaborative mapping functionalities to allow citizens to view, analyse and share data collected from different campaigns and create their own maps, individually and collaboratively. In addition, citizens can participate in on-going LandSense campaigns using their own devices (e.g. mobile phones and tablets), through interactive reporting and gaming applications, as well as launching their own campaigns.

This interaction is achieved by bringing together and extending various key pieces of technology like: Geo-Wiki, LACO-Wiki, Geopedia, Sentinel Hub and the Earth Observation Data Centre. The LandSense Engagement Platform, as described in this document provides the technical and legal basis to demonstrate the LandSense objective. The LandSense Engagement Platform can be accessed via <https://lep.landense.eu>

Figure 1: Building blocks of the LandSense Engagement Platform

2.1 LandSense Authorization Server

The LandSense Authorization Server is part of the LandSense Engagement Platform and acts as a broker of user authentication and personal information between the Identity Providers of the LandSense Federation and the operators of registered applications and services. Each operator of registered applications and/or services can obtain a specific amount of personal information, individual for each application and service that they register.

The LandSense Authorization Server controls the provision of the collected personal information from users to operators' applications based on scopes. The amount of personal information that an operator can fetch is based on the scope(s) the application was registered with. Which scopes exist and which user attributes are linked with a scope can be determined from this page <https://as.landense.eu/Scopes>

This Service does not collect any more personal information as received from an Identity Provider as previously authorized by the user at login with the Identity Provider.

The LandSense Authorization Server is available at <https://as.landense.eu>

2.1.1 Privacy Aspects

As a Horizon 2020 project, LandSense will adhere to the EU General Data Protection Regulation¹ (GDPR) coming into force on 25 May 2018. For the LandSense Authorization Server it is required that registered

¹ <https://www.eugdpr.org/>

applications and services collect and process personal data according to the GDPR. But in particular, the LandSense Authorization Server must be compliant with the GDPR. In order to ensure personal data collection and processing for applications and services, a URL to the Privacy Statement of the application / service must be provided when registering it with the LandSense Authorization Server. When users execute a registered application, they get asked to authorize the application to collect and process personal data as outlined in the Privacy Statement linked. The objective of the LandSense Authorization Server is to collect only relevant and necessary personal information of users after their authorization at login and make that information available to registered applications and services. The LandSense Authorization Server Privacy Statement is available at <https://as.landsense.eu/PrivacyStatement>

2.1.2 Terms of Use Aspects

The LandSense Authorization Server Terms of Use determine the conditions under which an application or service can be used. For the LandSense Engagement Platform, each application and service that is registered with the LandSense Authorization Server, a URL to the Terms of Use applicable to the application or service, must be provided. When a user is asked to authorize an application, the user can review the Terms of Use prior to stating agreement. The Terms of Use are available at <https://as.landsense.eu/TermsOfUse>

2.2 LandSense Federation

The LandSense Engagement Platform provides applications, services and tools to undertake citizen-driven science within the environmental domain of LULC. The LandSense offerings are free of charge but require a user to authenticate. The LandSense Federation supports users to authenticate from a variety of Identity Providers including social media, organizations and academic institutions participating in eduGAIN. Figure 2 provides an overview of academic federations worldwide participating in eduGAIN.

Figure 2: World map showing eduGAIN members [source: <https://technical.edugain.org/status>]

Additional details about the LandSense Federation are available at <https://lep.landsense.eu/Project/Federation>

2.3 LandSense Core Services

The LandSense Engagement Platform consists of several core services that are valuable to not only support citizen science campaigns within LandSense but also outside of the project across various domains. The specific exploitation strategies for these core services are to be elaborated within WP6 in the upcoming months. In addition, an innovative aspect of the LandSense framework allows more services registered with the LandSense Authorization Server to be ingested into the platform. Even though these services can be used in applications to support citizen science campaigns, these services would not be considered “core services” of LandSense. For additional details about the core services, please visit <https://lep.landense.eu/Innovate>

2.3.1 Development Support

The development support ensures that organizations participating in LandSense and interested parties (not restricted to be a LandSense partner) can develop applications and services that can be registered with the LandSense Authorization Server. The development support consists of different GitHub repositories as templates that show how to integrate the OAuth2 related functionality require to work with the LandSense Authorization Server. The initial support focuses on two different types of applications:

- Client-side web-applications implemented in JavaScript, leveraging the popular open-source library HelloJS², and
- Server-side web-applications built in ASP.NET Core using the OpenID Connect library as part of the open-source ASP.NET Security middleware³.

2.3.2 Change Detector Service

The LandSense Change Detector Service (CDS) integrates and build upon the existing Sentinel 2 image processing chain (i.e. processing and change detection). The objective of the CDS is to provide near real-time high quality LULC classifications, improved by the interactive exchange between authoritative EO data and citizen-observed in-situ data.

2.3.3 Quality Service

This service provides a range of quality assurance measures that can be applied in real-time and to post-data collection of LULC information, organized into processing workflows that will be customized for each demonstration case. It builds upon the open source quality assurance and control service developed in the previous FP7-funded COBWEB citizen observatory, adding the additional measures needed for LULC data.

2.3.4 Licensing Ontology

Each application and service, registered with the LandSense, is able to process the data contributed by users. In order to guarantee a maximum reuse and combined use of the data sets created in LandSense campaigns, it is required to select a Creative Commons (CC) license instance when registering an application or service with the LandSense Authorization Server.

The developed LandSense Licensing Ontology allows to determine programmatically the conditions under which data sets can be combined or used together. In particular, the LandSense Licensing Calculator allows answering these questions:

² <https://github.com/MrSwitch/hello.js>

³ <https://github.com/aspnet/Security>

- 1) You have two or more existing data sets with associated CC license instances that you want to combine. Question to solve: Which are the resulting licenses when you combine the data sets?
- 2) You have one or more existing data sets with associated CC license instances and you want to combine them with the result from a LandSense campaign such that a particular license can be put on the resulting data set. Which are the possible licenses that you can associate with the campaign?

The result for both licensing challenges could either an empty set that would indicate that these data sets couldn't be combined; or, the result could be a set of possible license instances to select from.

2.4 LandSense Campaigns

The explore section of the LandSense Engagement Platform allows the users to discover and directly contribute to ongoing LandSense campaigns. Users can access the landSense campaigns on via <https://lep.landSense.eu/Explore>

3 Legal Aspects

The LandSense Engagement Platform allows users to participate in LULC campaigns. Legal aspects arise when using a LandSense application to contribute in a campaign:

- Terms of Use are required to describe the conditions under which a user can participate via an application of a service.
- Privacy Statement is required to determine the collection and processing of personal information of users that login to the LandSense Engagement Platform or a registered application or service.
- Licensing Ontology is required to set the conditions under which the contributions of users will be processed by services of the LandSense Engagement Platform.

Legal information regarding the LandSense Engagement Platform is available at <https://lep.landSense.eu/Legal>